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Impact of Educational Policy Changes on Quality Education in Public Secondary Schools in Benue State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of educational policy changes on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and Two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 3,672 teachers from 303 public secondary schools in Benue State. A sample of 404 respondents from 33 public secondary schools was drawn using proportionate stratified and simple random sampling techniques. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire structured by the researcher titled "Educational Policy Changes and Quality Education Questionnaire (EPCQEQ)". Three experts from Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University ensured the validity of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through a trial-test which yielded a Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.89. The data collected were analyzed using Mean Scores and Standard Deviation to answer research questions and chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness of fit to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that assessment reforms and universal Basic Education (UBE) have significant positive impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. It was concluded that educational policy changes have significant positive impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. From the findings, it was recommended among others that the government should deepen assessment reforms by funding continuous assessment and teacher-training systems. This can be done by providing standardized tools, monitoring compliance, and supporting schools with resources.

Keywords: Policy changes, quality education, assessment reforms, universal basic education

INTRODUCTION

The quality of education delivered in secondary schools is globally recognized as a critical determinant of national development, human capital formation, and competitiveness in the knowledge-driven world economy. Across developed and developing nations, governments seem to continually reform educational policies to improve learning outcomes, enhance teacher quality, and strengthen school infrastructure in response to evolving global demands. In Nigeria, particularly in Benue State, public secondary schools are tasked with preparing students for further education and equipping them with the knowledge and skills needed to thrive in an increasingly competitive global environment. However, the quality of education in these schools has come under scrutiny in recent years, with stakeholders expressing concern

over declining performance indicators, infrastructural deficits, and inadequate teacher competence (Ityavyar & Agba, 2022). One of the critical factors influencing educational quality is the policy framework guiding the operations of public secondary schools (Ofojebe & Ezugoh, 2018). Policy changes, whether in curriculum design, teacher recruitment, funding allocation or infrastructural development seem to have the potential to impact quality education.

Quality education refers to an inclusive, equitable, and learner-centered approach to teaching and learning that equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes necessary to contribute meaningfully to society (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO, 2017). In Nigeria, quality education emphasizes access, relevance and outcomes, focusing on improving literacy rates, practical skills and critical thinking. For example, the National Policy on Education highlights the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to foster digital literacy and bridge the global knowledge gap (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2020). Additionally, initiatives such as the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme aim to enhance infrastructural development, teacher training, and learning materials, particularly in rural areas, addressing disparities in educational quality (Ofojebe & Ezugoh, 2018). Despite these efforts, challenges like underfunding, inadequate teacher-student ratios and outdated curricula persist, underscoring the need for sustainable policy changes to ensure equitable and effective learning outcomes across the nation.

Policy refers to a deliberate set of principles, guidelines or courses of action adopted by an organization or government to direct decision-making and achieve desired goals (Policy, 2014). It provides a framework that shapes behaviour, allocates resources and coordinates activities within systems to ensure consistency and accountability (Olorunfemi & Adedeji, 2020). Policies are often formalized through documents, regulations or statutes that outline expected actions and standards for addressing societal issues. Effective policies are evidence-based, clearly articulated and adaptable to changing conditions, enabling institutions to function efficiently and achieve expected outcomes (Okeke & Nwankwo, 2019). This foundational understanding of policy is essential for appreciating how these principles translate into the specialized domain of educational policy.

Educational policy refers to the collection of rules, regulations and guidelines formulated by governments or educational authorities to guide the management, operation and improvement of the education sector (Ogunyemi & Oni, 2019). It specifies the standards, structures and practices that influence curriculum design, teacher deployment, funding, assessment and quality assurance processes (Dauda & Adamu, 2021). Educational policies are developed to ensure equitable access, relevance, efficiency and accountability in teaching and learning, thereby promoting national development (Uzoagba & Ede, 2020). Effective educational policy implementation requires collaboration among stakeholders, adequate resources and continuous monitoring to ensure compliance and improvement. This conceptualization of educational policy builds on the general policy framework discussed earlier, demonstrating how broad policy principles are applied within the education system.

Changes in Educational policy refer to the deliberate adjustments or modifications made to existing frameworks, rules, or strategies to address emerging challenges, align with developmental goals, or improve outcomes in education (Adzongo, 2014). Policy changes as "the structured modifications to existing policies, programmes, or regulations, aimed at addressing evolving societal needs, improving service delivery, or adapting to new circumstances and challenges." This highlights the role of adaptability and service optimization in policymaking. Lasswell and McDougal (2020) view policy changes as "the deliberate recalibration of decision-making frameworks within a governance system, reflecting shifts in political priorities, economic realities, or cultural dynamics to achieve more equitable and effective outcomes." This definition emphasizes the interplay of governance and equity in policy adjustments.

The above changes are often informed by research, stakeholder consultations, or global trends, and they aim to create a more effective and inclusive system. For instance, the National Policy on Education (revised in 2020) emphasized the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into the curriculum to bridge the digital divide and enhance learning outcomes (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2020). Similarly, the introduction of the Treasury Single Account (TSA) in 2017 aimed to consolidate

revenue collection, minimize corruption, and ensure fiscal accountability in public institutions (Okonkwo & Uzodike, 2018). These examples illustrate the broad applicability of policy changes in Nigeria, targeting systemic inefficiencies and aligning with contemporary needs.

Specific policy changes have sought to address access and quality issues. The Universal Basic Education (UBE) Act (2004) underwent revisions to include provisions for improved teacher training and infrastructural development in rural areas, targeting the challenges of underqualified teaching personnel and inadequate learning environments (Ofojebe & Ezugoh, 2018). Additionally, the National Policy on Science and Technology introduced in 1986 and revised in 1997, 2003 and 2021 emphasized practical, research-based learning approaches in secondary and tertiary institutions to promote innovation and entrepreneurship among students (Adebayo, Ibrahim & Musa, 2021). There are several educational policy changes such as assessment reforms, universal Basic Education (UBE), integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching, National Language Policy and National Reading Framework as mentioned by Anderson (2015) could impact quality education in Nigeria, particularly in Benue State.

Assessment reforms in Nigeria refer to deliberate policy changes aimed at improving how students' learning outcomes are evaluated to ensure a more accurate measure of educational quality and effectiveness (Eze, Uche & Mba, 2022). These reforms include the integration of continuous assessment, competency-based evaluation, and the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to modernize the examination process (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2020). However, weaknesses in implementing these reforms, such as inadequate teacher training, inconsistent application of standards, and insufficient infrastructure, often undermine their effectiveness. For instance, many schools lack the technical capacity to conduct computer-based testing, leading to inequitable assessment practices and poor preparation of students for global competitiveness. Furthermore, corruption in examination administration, including widespread malpractice, compromises the integrity of assessments, thus failing to reflect the actual abilities of students (Oni, Adegbite & Aladejana, 2020). These shortcomings highlight how ineffective assessment reforms contribute to the challenges of quality education, as they distort the measurement of learning outcomes and hinder the identification of gaps that require intervention. This issue of ineffective assessments intersects with the broader challenges of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme, which also faces significant implementation hurdles.

The Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme, introduced in Nigeria in 1999 and later revised in 2004, aims to provide free, compulsory, and universal education for all children at the primary and junior secondary levels. The policy was designed to address issues of access, equity, and quality in education, focusing on increasing enrollment rates, reducing illiteracy, and enhancing infrastructure and teacher training (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2020). However, the quest for quality education in Nigeria seems to be hampered by weaknesses in the implementation of UBE. Challenges such as inadequate funding, poor teacher-student ratios, insufficient teaching materials, and weak monitoring mechanisms have undermined the policy's objectives (Obi, Ugwu & Adewale, 2020). For instance, many rural schools under the UBE programme lack basic infrastructure like classrooms and laboratories, unqualified teachers, over population of students, making it difficult to deliver quality education (Iorver, Terwase & Agbo, 2020). Addressing these weaknesses is critical to improving the quality of education in Nigeria. Similarly, these challenges are further exacerbated by the limitations in the implementation integration of ICT in teaching. Despite numerous policy changes, educational quality seems to continually face challenges, including insufficient infrastructure, undertrained teachers, and ineffective assessment strategies. It is against this background that the study sought to investigate the impact of educational policy changes on the quality of education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Quality education, as emphasized globally, is the foundation for improving lives and achieving sustainable development, and it encompasses inclusive, equitable and lifelong learning opportunities for all (UNESCO, 2020). However, in Nigeria, particularly in public secondary schools, stakeholders have consistently expressed concern over the declining quality of education, citing poor student outcomes, inadequate facilities and limited teacher competence. These concerns seem to have been echoed across

various educational forums, reflecting growing dissatisfaction with the effectiveness of policy-driven interventions in the education sector.

In Benue State, the researcher observed alarming issues undermining quality education in public secondary schools. These include dilapidated infrastructure, lack of instructional materials and the presence of underqualified teachers; conditions that point to poor implementation of key education policies such as the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme. Additionally, there is growing concern of students being poorly prepared for higher education and the labour market, suggesting a disconnect between national curriculum reforms and the region's contextual educational needs. These challenges could be closely linked to the inconsistencies resulting from frequent policy changes that often lack proper planning, evaluation and adaptation to local realities. While government and stakeholders have made commendable efforts to improve education through funding initiatives, teacher development programmes and curricular reforms (Federal Ministry of Education, 2022) these efforts seem not to have yielded the expected outcomes. The researcher still observes persistent issues such as ineffective teaching practices, curriculum irrelevance and student disengagement, raising concerns about the practical impact of policy changes on educational quality. This persistent mismatch between policy intent and actual school-level realities justifies the need for this study. The problem of this study put in question form thus; what is the impact of educational policy changes on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate impact of educational policy changes on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the impact of assessment reforms on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.
2. ascertain the impact of Universal Basic Education (UBE) on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the impact of assessment reforms on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of Universal Basic Education on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Assessment reforms have no significant impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.
2. Universal Basic Education has no significant impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHOD

Ex-post factor design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 3,672 teachers from 303 public secondary schools in Benue State. A sample of 404 respondents from 33 public secondary schools was drawn using proportionate stratified and simple random sampling techniques. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire structured by the researcher titled "Educational Policy Changes and Quality Education Questionnaire (EPCQEQ)". Three experts from Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University ensured the validity of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through a trial-test which yielded a Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.89. Data were collected by the researcher with the help of four research assistants.

The data generated for the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions whereby a cut-off point of 2.50 and above was taken as positive response and agreed; while any Mean Score less than 2.50 was taken as negative response and disagreed. Chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness-of-fit was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of

significance. Chi-square (χ^2) is appropriate for this study because it is a non-parametric statistics for treating data as it permits the researcher to determine whether or not a significant impact exists between the observed number of cases falling into each category and the expected number of cases based on the null hypotheses (Akhtar, 2016). The decision rule for rejection or otherwise of the hypotheses was based on p value and alpha value. Hypotheses of no significant impact was not rejected for any hypothesis whose p value was equal to or greater than alpha value of 0.05 ($p \geq 0.05$). While any hypothesis whose p value is less than alpha value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) was rejected.

RESULTS

Question One: *What is the impact of assessment reforms on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: *Mean and Standard Deviation of Impact of Assessment Reforms on Quality Education in Public Secondary Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.*

S/No	Items Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	Assessment reforms improve students' learning outcomes.	392	84	197	70	41	2.83	0.89	Agree
2	Continuous assessment is now more objective.	392	91	270	20	11	3.13	0.61	Agree
3	Assessment record-keeping reforms improves learning feedback.	392	132	131	80	49	2.88	1.02	Agree
4	Teacher training on assessment methods helps to increase instructional quality.	392	97	199	63	33	2.92	0.86	Agree
5	Assessment reforms has not promoted fair evaluation of students.	392	17	38	196	141	1.82	0.78	Disagree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation							2.72	0.96	Agree

Source: *Researchers' Field Survey Results (2025)*

Table 1 shows that the Mean ratings of item 1-5 are 2.83, 3.13, 2.88, 2.92 and 1.82 with the corresponding Standard Deviations of 0.89, 0.61, 1.02, 0.86 and 0.78 respectively. Based on the decision rule, item 1, 2, 3 and 4 were above the cut-off mark of 2.50, while item 5 was below the cut-off mark. This indicates that, Assessment reforms improve students' learning outcomes. The respondents agreed that continuous assessment is now more objective and that assessment record-keeping reforms improves learning feedback. The respondents also agreed that teacher training on assessment methods helps to increase instructional quality. However, the respondent disagreed of the item that assessment reforms has not promoted fair evaluation of students. The cluster mean of 2.72 was above the cut-off point of 2.50 and the cluster standard deviation of 0.96 which indicated that most responses are close to the mean. This means that assessment reforms have positive impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Question Two: *What is the impact of Universal Basic Education on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: *Mean and Standard Deviation for Impact of Universal Basic Education on Quality Education in Public Secondary Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.*

S/No	Items Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
6	UBE infrastructure support has improved classroom learning conditions.	392	101	124	95	72	2.65	1.06	Agree
7	UBE training programmes have enhanced teacher instructional quality.	392	114	183	56	39	2.95	0.91	Agree
8	UBE provision of learning materials has boosted students' academic performance.	392	88	166	72	66	2.70	1.00	Agree
9	UBE school feeding programme has not increased students' attendance to schools.	392	71	89	128	104	2.32	1.06	Disagree
10	UBE monitoring has improved school performance standards.	392	27	280	61	24	2.79	0.65	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation							2.69	0.97	Agree

Source: *Researchers' Field Survey Results (2025)*

Table 2 shows that the Mean ratings of items 6-10 are 2.65, 2.95, 2.70, 2.32 and 2.79 with the corresponding standard deviations of 1.06, 0.91, 1.00, 1.06 and 0.65 respectively. Based on the decision rule, item 6, 7, 8 and 10 were above the cut-off mark of 2.50, while item 9 was below the cut-off mark. This implies that Universal Basic Education improved quality education. Item by item analysis showed that UBE infrastructure support has improved classroom learning conditions and UBE training programmes have enhanced teacher instructional quality. Respondents agreed unanimously that UBE provision of learning materials has boosted students' academic performance. The respondents disagreed with the item that UBE school feeding programme has not increased students' attendance to schools. On the other hand, the respondents agreed with the item which states that UBE monitoring has improved school performance standards. The cluster mean of 2.69 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 and the cluster standard deviation of 0.97 which indicated that most responses are close to the mean. This means that Universal Basic Education has positive impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1: Assessment reforms have no significant impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Table 3:

Chi-square Analysis of the Significant Impact of Assessment Reforms on Quality Education in Public Secondary Schools in Benue State, Nigeria

Responses	SA	A	D	SD	Df	P	Decision
Observed Frequency	84	167	86	55			
					3	0.003	Rejected
Expected Frequency	98	98	98	98			

$P=.003 < 0.05; df=3$

Table 3 shows that $P < .05$ with 3 degree of freedom. This shows that the null hypothesis which states that assessment reforms have no significant impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue

State, Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This result clearly shows that assessment reforms have significant positive impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: Universal Basic Education has no significant impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Table 4: *Chi-square Analysis of the Significant Impact of Universal Basic Education on Quality Education in Public Secondary Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.*

Responses	SA	A	D	SD	Df	P	Decision
Observed Frequency	81	168	82	61			
					3	0.000	Rejected
Expected Frequency	98	98	98	98			

$P=.000 < 0.05$; $df=3$

Table 4 shows that $P < .05$ with 3 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that Universal Basic Education has no significant impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria was rejected. This implies that Universal Basic Education has significant positive impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This research work investigated impact of educational policy changes on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. The findings of the study are discussed as follows:

The first finding revealed that assessment reforms have significant positive impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. The finding that assessment reforms significantly enhance quality education in Benue State aligns strongly with empirical studies emphasizing the transformative influence of modern assessment practices on learning outcomes. For instance, Oni, Adegbite and Aladejana (2020) found out that formative assessments such as quizzes, classwork and project-based tasks significantly improve students’ academic achievement, which supports the present finding because formative assessments constitute a key part of current assessment reforms in Nigeria. Similarly, Eze, Uche and Mba (2022) found that policy-level assessment reforms increased student engagement, improved instructional strategies and shifted schools from rote learning to competency-based approaches outcomes that directly mirror quality indicators examined in the present study. These studies justify the current finding by demonstrating that when assessment reforms emphasize continuous assessment, timely feedback, learner-centred evaluation and performance tracking, they enhance both teaching and learning effectiveness. The relevance of these studies to the present research also lies in their methodological similarity, since all used structured questionnaires to collect data from teachers, thus making the findings comparable. Although the studies were carried out in Ogun and Enugu States, their conclusions support the present study by proving that assessment reforms exert consistent positive influences across different Nigerian contexts. Therefore, the finding is justified as assessment reforms foster deeper learning, improved monitoring of student progress and alignment of instruction with curriculum standards, all of which significantly boost quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State.

The second finding revealed that Universal Basic Education has significant positive impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. The finding that Universal Basic Education (UBE) positively influences quality education in Benue State is reinforced by several empirical studies emphasizing its role in improving access, infrastructure and instructional delivery. Obi, Ugwu and Adewale (2020) revealed that UBE enhances teacher professional development, instructional material availability and school infrastructure all of which are key determinants of educational quality examined in the present study. Their findings correspond with the present result by showing that UBE interventions

strengthen core components of quality education such as improved classroom conditions and increased learning opportunities. Similarly, the finding of the study is in line with Iorver, Terwase and Agbo (2022), who conducted their study specifically in Benue State, found that UBE contributed significantly to classroom renovation, construction of new buildings, provision of furniture and improvements in student achievement. This direct geographical alignment makes their study closely relevant and provides strong justification for the present finding, since both studies report similar patterns among secondary schools in Benue State. These empirical revelations validate the present finding by showing that UBE not only widens access but also enhances the learning environment, teaching effectiveness and student outcomes. Although implementation challenges such as funding inconsistencies exist, the overall positive impact of UBE on quality education is well supported, demonstrating that its interventions play a significant role in strengthening educational systems within Benue State.

CONCLUSION

This study established that educational policy changes have significant positive impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. Therefore, educational policy changes in the areas of assessment reforms and universal Basic Education (UBE) have significant positive impact on quality education in public secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government should deepen assessment reforms by funding continuous assessment and teacher-training systems. This can be done by providing standardized tools, monitoring compliance, and supporting schools with resources. The expected result is improved learning outcomes, better instructional practices, and more reliable evaluation of student performance across public secondary schools.
2. Educational policy planners should strengthen UBE implementation by reviewing gaps and introducing evidence-based policy adjustments. This should be done through stakeholder consultations, data-driven evaluation, and improved funding structures. The expected outcome is enhanced access, improved learning environments, and sustained quality education delivery in Benue State secondary schools.

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